

COMPARISON OF TOXICITIES BETWEEN CISPLATIN-ETOPOSIDE VERSUS PACLITAXEL-CARBOPLATIN REGIMEN ALONG WITH THORACIC RADIOTHERAPY IN UNRESECTABLE LOCALLY ADVANCED NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER

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ABSTRACT

Background: Combined modality of treatment i.e., platinum-based doublet chemotherapy with concurrent radiotherapy is the standard treatment for locally advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). However, the optimal chemotherapy regimen to use with radiotherapy is still not established. Aim of this study was to compare the acute toxicities between cisplatin-etoposide (EP) and paclitaxel-carboplatin (PC) along with thoracic radiotherapy in unresectable locally advanced NSCLC. **Materials and Methods:** A Quasi-experimental study was conducted from October 2020 to September 2021 at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) and National Institute of Cancer Research and Hospital (NICR&H), Dhaka. Patients with unresectable, locally advanced NSCLC who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled and distributed equally into two arms. Patients received thoracic radiotherapy with 60Gy in 2Gy daily fractions, 5 fractions a week, for 6 weeks with either Injection Cisplatin 50 mg/m² administered on days 1, 8, 29, and 36, and Injection Etoposide 50 mg/m²/day on days 1–5 and 29–33 (Arm A), or Injection Carboplatin (AUC-2) and Injection Paclitaxel (45 mg/m²) administered on day 1, weekly, over a 6-week period (Arm B). All the patients were evaluated before, during, and after the completion of the treatment. Follow ups were done at 6 weeks, 12 weeks and 24 weeks following the completion of treatment using history, clinical examination and investigations. **Results:** most commonly observed toxicities were nausea, esophagitis and radiation pneumonitis. Although grade 1 esophagitis was more in arm B (56.76% vs 35.14%), grade 2 and 3 esophagitis were more in arm A (40.54% vs 16.21%; and 13.51% vs 5.41% respectively; p 0.043). Grade 1 pneumonitis was same (16 or 43.24%) in both arms. However, Grade 2 and 3 radiation pneumonitis were significantly more in Arm B (40.54% vs 16.22% and 5.41% vs 2.7 % respectively; p 0.004). Observed differences in nausea, vomiting, dermatitis, neurotoxicity, and hematological toxicities were not found to be statistically significant. **Conclusion:** This study suggests that the toxicities of cisplatin-etoposide regimen is comparable to paclitaxel-carboplatin regimen when given with concurrent radiotherapy in unresectable locally advanced non-small cell lung cancer.

KEYWORDS: Lung cancer, Concurrent chemoradiation, Non-small cell lung cancer, Locally advanced, Cisplatin and etoposide, Carboplatin and Paclitaxel.

INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer is the second most common malignancy and the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide.^[1] Although such statistics are not currently available for Bangladesh, according to the Hospital Based Cancer Registry report (2015-2017) by the NICR&H, lung was the leading site of cancers (5887, 16.6%).^[2]

Although the exact cause of lung cancer is not known, around 80%-90% lung cancer cases are attributable to voluntary/involuntary exposure to cigarette smoking.^[3] Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is the main

histologic type (80-85%).^[4] When there is invasion of adjacent structures and/or lymph node metastases it is not amenable for potentially curative resection.^[5] Around 35% of NSCLC present with such locally advanced diseases.^[6] Locally advanced NSCLC include unresectable stage II to III diseases and selected patients with stage II to III disease who are surgical candidates.^[7]

In treatment of locally advanced NSCLC, chemoradiation has survival benefit over radiotherapy alone but the optimal chemoradiation regimen is a work in progress.^[3,8] Concurrent administrations of the

chemotherapy and radiotherapy has better local response as well as survival benefit when compared to sequential administration of these therapies. But this strategy has greater acute toxicity like acute esophagitis.^[6]

Various combination regimens have been trialed with concurrent RT in phase III randomized studies. However, very few randomized phase III trials have directly compared the different CCRT regimens.^[9]

Etoposide-cisplatin (EP) and paclitaxel-carboplatin (PC) are two very widely used regimens; also, here in Bangladesh. A recent randomized trial showed better response rate as well as a significant benefit in overall survival with EP arm (28.0% vs 19.7%).^[9] On the other hand, there have been some meta-analyses and systematic reviews which showed comparable outcomes in terms of response and survival in both while the toxicity profile favored the PC regimen.^[10]

Common toxicities of concurrent chemoradiation including neutropenia, acute esophagitis, radiation pneumonitis, skin toxicities, etc. Nausea and vomiting are also frequently observed.^[9,11]

While all oncology centers have their own commonly prescribed regimens there are no definitive data to support their preferences, especially in this part of the world. Therefore, the aim of this study is to compare the toxicity profile of these two drug regimens and to help in future treatment decisions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This Quasi-experimental study was conducted from October 2020 to September 2021 in the Department of Clinical Oncology, BSMMU and Department of Radiation Oncology, NICR&H, Dhaka. Total 74 patients with histologically proven unresectable locally advanced NSCLC of stage IIIA, IIIB & IIIC were enrolled in the study. The study was carried out in line with the Helsinki Declaration. Ethical approval was secured from respective institutions. Informed consent was obtained

from each patient before collecting data. Data were collected using a structured data collection form by face-to-face interviews with patients, and from their history and investigation reports.

Patients were distributed equally into two arms using purposive sampling. All patients received thoracic radiotherapy of 60Gy in 2Gy daily fractions, 5 fractions a week, for 6 weeks using 6 MV photon from LINAC machine with concurrent chemotherapy. Patients in arm-A received intravenous Cisplatin 50 mg/m² administered on days 1, 8, 29, 36 and Etoposide 50 mg/m²/day on days 1–5 and 29–33. Arm-B patients received intravenous Carboplatin (AUC-2) and Paclitaxel (45 mg/m²) administered on day 1, weekly, over a 6-week period concurrently with radiotherapy.^[9,12,13]

All the patients were evaluated before, during, and after the completion of the treatment. Follow ups were done at 6 weeks, 12 weeks and 24 weeks following the completion of treatment. Toxicities were assessed by clinical examination and relevant investigations like complete blood count and chest radiogram. We looked for nausea-vomiting, hematological toxicities (Anemia, Neutropenia, Thrombocytopenia), skin reactions, mucositis, esophagitis, pneumonitis, diarrhea and peripheral neuropathy. Toxicities were assessed using the national cancer institute's Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events, version 5.0.^[14] The data were analyzed using the SPSS software program (North Castle, NY, USA) for Windows, version 25. A p value of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 74 patients were enrolled in this study. Table-1 summarizes the baseline characteristics of patients in the two arms. There were no statistically significant differences between the two arms in terms of age, gender, body surface area (BSA), performance status, or stage (p-value > 0.05). As per inclusion criteria no patients with metastasis (M1) or ECOG performance status 3 were included in the study.

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to the baseline character.

Variable	Arm A (n = 37)	Arm B (n = 37)	Total (n = 74)	p-value*
Age (years)				
Mean (SD)	61.43 (±5.87)	61.32 (±5.84)	61.38 (±5.82)	0.937
Range	25 (45-70)	20 (49-69)	25 (45-70)	
Gender				
Male	30 (81.1%)	27 (73%)	57 (77%)	0.581
Female	7 (18.9%)	10 (27%)	17 (23%)	
BSA (m²)				
Mean (SD)	1.615 (±0.1185)	1.603 (±0.1138)	1.604 (±0.1154)	0.944
Range	0.46 (1.35-1.81)	0.44 (1.36-1.80)	0.44 (1.36-1.80)	
ECOG performance status				
1	24 (64.9%)	21 (56.8%)	45 (60.8%)	0.634
2	13 (35.1%)	16 (43.2%)	29 (39.2%)	
Histology				0.351

Adenocarcinoma	22 (59.46%)	18 (48.64%)	40 (54.05%)	0.095
Squamous cell carcinoma	15 (40.54%)	19 (51.36%)	34 (45.95%)	
Stage (AJCC 8th edition)				
IIIA	19 (51.35%)	10 (27.03%)	29 (39.19%)	
IIIB	16 (43.24%)	23 (62.16%)	39 (52.70%)	
IIIC	2 (5.41%)	4 (10.81%)	6 (8.11%)	

* Calculated using Student's t test or chi-square (χ^2) test

ECOG = Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group, AJCC = American Joint Committee on Cancer

The patients were aged 45 to 70 years and were mostly men (77%). Their mean age at diagnosis was 61.43 years in arm A and 61.32 years in arm B. Most patients in both arms had an ECOG performance rating of 1 (64.9% in Arm A and 56.8% in Arm B). Histologically both

adenocarcinomas and squamous cell carcinomas were almost equally distributed in both arms. Arm-A patients had more adenocarcinomas than arm-B. The most prevalent disease stage was IIIB (52.7%).

p = 0.619

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to their habit of smoking in both arms.

Most of the patients were smokers (50 or 67.57%). Figure-1 depicts that 70.27 % patients in arm A and 64.86% in arm B had a history of smoking tobacco. Most common presentation in both arms was cough: 51 (68.91%) followed by chest pain: 28 (37.83%) and shortness of breath: 26 (35.14%). Figure-2 shows

common symptoms and signs in both arms. Majority of patient in Arm A presented with cough (64.86%) followed by chest pain (56.75%), whereas patients in Arm B presented with cough (72.97%) and SOB (37.84%). There was no significant difference between the two arms (p>0.05).

SOB = shortness of breath, SVCO = superior vena cava obstruction

Toxicities

Nausea was the most common toxicity while esophagitis was the most severe one. Frequency of esophagitis has been shown in figure-2. Grade 1, 2, and 3 Esophagitis

was seen in 13(35.14%), 15(40.54%), and 5(13.51%) patients in Arm A and 21(56.76%), 6(16.21%), and 2(5.41%) patients in Arm B respectively. This difference was statistically significant (p 0.043).

Table-2 shows other measured toxicities in both arms in this study. Radiation pneumonitis was frequently observed after treatment completion (75.67%). It was significantly less in arm-A ($p = 0.004$). Although sixteen

patients (43.24%) developed grade 1 pneumonitis in both arms, 37.84% patients in arm-A didn't develop any. Only a few patients developed grade 3 pneumonitis: 1(2.71%) in Arm A and 2 (5.41%) in Arm B.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to toxicities in both arms.

Toxicities	Arm A (n = 37)	Arm B (n = 37)	Total (n = 74)	p-value*
Pneumonitis				0.004
Grade 0	14 (37.84%)	4 (10.81%)	18 (24.33%)	
Grade 1	16 (43.24%)	16 (43.24%)	32 (43.24%)	
Grade 2	6 (16.22%)	15 (40.54%)	23 (31.08%)	
Grade 3	1 (2.7%)	2 (5.41%)	1 (1.35%)	
Skin toxicity				0.04
Grade 0	7 (18.91%)	4 (10.81%)	11 (14.87%)	
Grade 1	17 (45.95%)	23 (62.16%)	40 (54.05%)	
Grade 2	13 (35.14%)	10 (27.03%)	23 (31.08%)	
Nausea				0.223
Grade 0	3(8.10%)	6(16.23%)	9(12.16%)	
Grade 1	28(75.67%)	21(56.76%)	49(66.22%)	
Grade 2	6(16.23%)	10(27.01%)	16(21.62%)	
Vomiting				0.614
Grade 0	7(18.92%)	10(27.03%)	17(22.97%)	
Grade 1	19(51.35%)	22(59.46%)	41(55.41%)	
Grade 2	11(29.73%)	5(13.51%)	16(21.62%)	
Anemia				0.391
Grade 0	10(27.03%)	12(32.43%)	22(29.73%)	
Grade 1	20(54.05%)	22(59.46%)	42(56.75%)	
Grade 2	7(18.92%)	3(8.11%)	10(13.51%)	
Neutropenia				0.129
Grade 0	3(8.11%)	6(16.22%)	9(12.16%)	
Grade 1	16(43.24%)	21(56.75%)	37(50.00%)	
Grade 2	15(40.54%)	10(27.03%)	25(33.78%)	
Grade 3	3(8.11%)	0	3(4.06%)	
Thrombocytopenia				0.545
Grade 0	19(51.35%)	21(56.76%)	31(41.89%)	
Grade 1	15(40.54%)	11(29.73%)	25(33.78%)	
Grade 2	3(8.11%)	5(13.51%)	8(10.81%)	
Neurotoxicity				0.183
Absent	30 (81.08%)	25 (67.57%)	55 (74.32%)	
Grade 1	7 (18.92%)	12 (32.43%)	19 (25.68%)	

* Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test

Grade 0 = Not present

More than half of the patients (54.05%) developed grade 1 skin toxicity. In Arm A, 17(45.95%) and 13(35.14%) patients developed grade 1 and 2 dermatitis respectively. In Arm B, 23(62.16%) and 10(27.03%) patients developed grade 1 and 2 dermatitis respectively. Nausea was the most common toxicity occurring in more than 66% patients. Vomiting was also common. No statistically significant difference was found between two groups regarding these ($p > 0.05$).

Hematological toxicities were observed during treatment with the distribution shown in table-2. Grade 1, 2 and 3 Neutropenia were present in 16(43.24%), 15(40.54%) and 3(8.11%) patients respectively in Arm A. In Arm B 21(56.75%) and 10(27.03%) patients developed Grade 1 and 2 Neutropenia respectively, but none developed Grade 3 Neutropenia. Anemia and Thrombocytopenia were similarly present in both arms. No statistically significant result was found between two groups ($p > 0.05$).

Only 7(18.92%) patients in Arm A and 12(32.43%) patients in Arm B showed grade 1 neurotoxicity. Rest of the patients showed no toxicity ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

The mean age of patients in Arm A was 61.43 years and that in Arm B was 61.32 years. Among them 77% were male and 23% female. These demographics were similar to the Hospital Cancer Registry Report 2015-2017, NICR&H where around 85 percent of total lung cancer patients were male and around 15% of them were female.^[2] This finding was also similar to that of Bi *et al.*^[15]

Smoking, which is established as a major independent risk factor for lung cancer, was commonly observed in this study. Arm A had 26(70.27%) patients and Arm B had 24(64.86%) patients who were smokers, and this mainly comprised of male patients.

The overall common presentation in both the groups was cough: 51(68.91%). It was present in 24 (64.86%) patients in Arm A and 27 (72.97%) patients in Arm B. Next were chest pain, breathlessness, and hemoptysis. The finding was similar to the observation of Corner, 2005 where cough, breathlessness, and chest pain were the most common presentations. A significant number of patients *i.e.*, 12(16.22%) presented with severe features like SVCO. Such patients with SVCO, were initially managed conservatively with Oxygen supplementation, steroids, bronchodilators, diuretics, etc. Then, after improvement of the symptoms, they were continued with the normal treatment protocol.

All patients were assessed weekly for any toxicities during concurrent chemoradiotherapy period. Different types of toxicities *i.e.*, both hematological and non-hematological were observed during the therapy and on subsequent follow ups.

No patient in any arm was spared from at least 1 form of cytopenia. The differences between the arms were not significant regarding hematological toxicities. Grade 1 and grade 2 anemia was seen in 20(54.05%) and 7(18.92%) patients in Arm A and 22(59.46%) and 3(8.11%) in Arm B respectively. Neutropenia was quite common with overall Grade 1 and 2 Neutropenia developed by 37(50.00%) patients and 25(33.78%) patients respectively. Only 3(8.11%) patients in Arm A developed Grade 3 Neutropenia. Grade 1 Neutropenia was seen in 16(43.24%) patients in Arm A and in 21(56.75%) patients in Arm B while 15(40.54%) patients in Arm A and 10(27.03%) patients in Arm B developed Grade 2 Neutropenia. A systematic review done by Steuer *et al.*^[10] has similar findings where 54% patients in the EP arm (Arm A) and 23% in PC arm (Arm B) had Neutropenia where the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). This could be because the patients received prophylactic granulocyte – colony stimulating factor (G-CSF) depending on their weekly blood counts.

Commonly observed non-hematologic toxicities were esophagitis, radiation pneumonitis, and nausea. In Arm A, 15(40.54%) and 5(13.51%) patients developed grade 2 and 3 esophagitis respectively. In Arm B, 6(16.21%) and 2(5.41%) patients developed grade 2 and 3 esophagitis respectively. Here, the observed difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.043$). This finding supports the observation of Santana-Davila *et al.*^[11] where they found that mucositis/esophagitis was significantly more common in EP arm as compared to PC arm (18.6% vs 14.4%; $p = 0.0246$). Patients who developed severe esophagitis, mostly did so during the later weeks of CCRT. That is why we had very few treatment interruptions. Besides, good care was taken for such patients and also others, regarding their nutritional status and hydration along with other symptomatic treatment. Nasogastric tube was placed for a few patients (9.46%) to maintain their nutritional intake.

Radiation pneumonitis was quite common which mostly developed after the completion of treatment in both arms. Grade 1 and 2 pneumonitis occurred in 16(43.24%) and 9(24.32%) patients in arm A, and 12(32.43%) and 17(45.95%) patients in arm B, respectively. Only a few patients developed grade 3 pneumonitis: 1(2.71%) in Arm A and 4(10.81%) in Arm B. This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.004$). A similar observation was made by Liew *et al.*^[16] where they found that radiation pneumonitis was more common with PC regimen compared to EP regimen (66% vs 38%; $p = 0.033$). Various studies have considered paclitaxel-carboplatin regimen as an independent factor for radiation pneumonitis, although the exact reason hasn't yet been identified. As it was rarely found during treatment, there were only a few treatment interruptions and delays. Also, it was tedious at times to differentiate between tumor progression, or infection, or exacerbation of previous chronic illnesses with radiation pneumonitis.

Symptomatic treatment with rest, propped up position, bronchodilators, inhaled steroids etc. was usually sufficient for \leq grade 2 pneumonitis. However, for grade 3 radiation pneumonitis, patients needed oxygen and systemic administration of corticosteroids.

Similarly, nausea and vomiting also were quite commonly observed during treatment. In arm A 18(75.67%) patients showed grade 1 and 6(16.23%) showed grade 2 nausea whereas, arm B 21(56.76%) showed grade 1 and 10(27.02%) showed grade 2 nausea. Grade 1 vomiting was seen in 19(51.35%) and grade 2 in 11(29.73%) in arm A and in arm B 22(59.46%) patients showed grade 1 vomiting and 5(13.51%) patients showed grade 2 vomiting. Although statistically not significant, nausea and vomiting were found to be more common in Arm A. There were similar findings in the meta-analysis by Santana-Davila *et al.* which showed 13% patients in EP arm and 8.2% patients in PC arm developed nausea and vomiting.^[11] Despite optimal measures with prophylactic anti-emetics, a few patients developed severe vomiting. They were carefully managed with counselling, injectable anti-emetics, antacids, etc. as well as nutritional and hydration support.

Only around one-third patients developed radiation dermatitis and the observed difference between the two arms was not statistically significant. High megavoltage energy being used for RT could be the reason for a low percentage of patients developing skin toxicities. Neurotoxicity in the form of peripheral neuropathy was rarely observed. This is probably because the doses of chemotherapy used in CCRT are very low.

There were multiple limitations of this study. As it was a non-randomized quasi-experimental study selection bias was present. The time period was short to evaluate the outcomes like progression free survival or overall survival. This study doesn't reflect the nationwide scenario owing to a small sample size and to the fact that it was conducted in two centers of Dhaka city only.

CONCLUSION

Toxicities of cisplatin-etoposide (EP) is comparable to paclitaxel-carboplatin (PC) when given with concurrent radiotherapy in unresectable locally advanced non-small cell lung cancer. As significant esophagitis is more in EP regimen and radiation pneumonitis in PC regimen, patient selection based on comorbidities and risk factors is of utmost importance.

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